

Data management plan (DMP)

Implementing AutoML algorithm for Regression tasks

AutoML4Regression

[coverspace]

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	2022-04-28	First version of DMP – created for start of project (deliverable x.y)
2.0	2022-04-29	Second version of DMP – prepared for midterm review

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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, I followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make my data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- I will make my data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- I will make my data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- I will make my data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. I will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- I will make my data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published data sets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of data sets that will be reused or produced

Produced data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	METRO_INTERSTATE.ipynb	notebook	.ipynb	100 MB	no
P2	PARKINSONS_TELEMONITORING.ipynb	notebook	.ipynb	100 MB	no
P3	Portugal_Election.ipynb	notebook	.ipynb	100 MB	no
P4	config_ML.py	config	.py	100 MB	no
P5	ML_Regression_Presentation.pptx	plain text	.pptx	100 MB	no
P6	README.txt	Plain text	.txt	100 MB	no

Reused data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	DOI and license / source	contains sensitive data
P1	parkinsons_updrs.csv	plain text	.csv	100 MB	no
P2	Metro_Interstate_Traffic_Volume.csv	plain text	.csv	100 MB	no
P3	ElectionDataPortugal.csv	plain text	.csv	100 MB	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Data generation

Within this research project I will implement a simple AutoML algorithm for regression tasks using Python.

It will be developed for the purpose of automated selection of the best machine learning technique and configuration the best hyperparameters for a particular regression data set. This simple AutoML system will implement hill climbing search algorithm and will use the following three regression algorithms:

- RandomForestRegressor
- DecisionTreeRegressor
- LinearRegression

Furthermore, I will compare the results of my own AutoML system to other state of the art approaches such as:

- auto-sklearn
- TPOT

Data reuse

I will test my AutoML system on the following tree regression datasets from UCI Machine Learning Repository:

- Real-time Election Results: Portugal 2019 Data Set
(<http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Real-time+Election+Results%3A+Portugal+2019>)
- Metro Interstate Traffic Volume Data Set
(<http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Metro+Interstate+Traffic+Volume>)
- Parkinsons Telemonitoring Data Set
(<http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Parkinsons+Telemonitoring>)

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in [AutoML_for_Regression_tasks_30042022] and include a timestamp of creation. Version control is automated.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, I will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, I will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, I will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, I will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

Data quality checks will be done, e.g. checks of consistency of labels, logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 (parkinsons_updrs.csv) will be stored in TUGitLab: Git is a software for distributed Version management of files (especially of source code). With TUGitLab, TU.it provides an application for managing repositories based on Git. TU members with an active TUaccount can use this service when working on GitLab projects. In TUGitLab, institute administrators activated in the Online Account Management can manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and assign external project partners as additional GitLab users.

P3 (ElectionDataPortugal.csv) will be stored in TUpCloud: With our File Sync and Share service, your data can be stored in a "virtual TUpCloud" taking data security into account. The more extensive storage space that TUpCloud makes available to you for your projects is separate from and independent of your personal TUownCloud storage. In contrast to TUownCloud, people outside

TU can also be authorised to read and write TUprouCloud folders. Because data is stored on the servers of TU Wien, TUprouCloud also supports the secure exchange of data with external project partners.

P2 (Metro_Interstate_Traffic_Volume.csv) will be stored in TUfiles: With TUfiles, we give you the opportunity to store data on a central and readily available network drive with backup (hosted on Windows servers). TUfiles is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands. TUfiles is not suitable for applications demanding high storage performance for a long period of time, such as high-performance databases, computer applications with high data access requirements and for storing local Microsoft Outlook PST files and backups.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

I pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to the data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

Ethical issues in the project have been identified and discussed with the Research Ethics Coordinator at TU Wien (<https://www.tuwien.at/en/research/rti-support/research-ethics/>). They are described in detail in separate documents. The research has not been reviewed yet by any ethics committee.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns. Further data will be made available with restrictive access.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2022-05-30	TU Data		PDDL
P2	Open		2022-05-30	TU Data		PDDL
P3	Open		2022-05-30	TU Data		PDDL

The repository used in this project described in the following paragraph.

TU Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/>

Specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data: Auto-sklearn is supported neither on MAC nor on Windows yet. The framework is only supported on Ubuntu and Linux. In order to make the solution interoperable I will implement it in my Google Account using Google Drive and Google CoLab (the tool is pre-installed with Ubuntu). All required libraries and the way how to run the notebooks I will describe in README.

Description of protocol to access restricted data:

5b Long-term preservation and reusability

dataset ID	location for long-term storage (min. 10 years)	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Data	10 years	Students and general public
P2	TU Data	10 years	Students and general public
P3	TU Data	10 years	Students and general public

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Rauber will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Title	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0